

Supplementary Information

Manuscript title: TGF- β -induced CCR8 promoted macrophage transdifferentiation into myofibroblast-like cells

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Supplementary Figure S1

Fig. S1 Effects of TGF- β on MH-S cell viability.

(A and B) CCK8 assay results showing that the effects of TGF- β on the cell viability in MH-S cells.

The results indicated that both different doses of TGF- β and different time points of TGF- β treatment had no distinct effect on cell viability. Data are representative of at least 3 independent experiments.

Supplementary Figure S2

Fig. S2 Effects of TGF- β on the levels of macrophage-derived CCL1

(A and B) ELISAs suggested that TGF- β significantly decreased the CCL1 expression in a dose-dependent manner (A) and a time-dependent manner (B) in MH-S cells. Data are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M. (n=5); *P<0.05 versus the control group (Student's t-test).

Supplementary Figure S3

Fig. S3 Effects of 3-MA on the levels of autophagic proteins

(A and B) Representative Western blot and densitometric analyses showing that 1 mM 3-MA significantly inhibited the expression of LC3B and Beclin 1. Data are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M (n =3); *p < 0.05; **P<0.01 vs the control group; #p < 0.05 vs the TGF- β group. (one-way ANOVA).